

ECONOMIC SCIENCES

THE ROLE OF HUMAN RESOURCE POTENTIAL IN ENSURING THE HUMAN RESOURCE SECURITY OF ENTERPRISES IN THE CONTEXT OF EUROPEAN INTEGRATION, THE DEVELOPMENT OF SMART TECHNOLOGIES, AND COMPLIANCE CONTROL

Shevchenko N.

Ph.D. (Economics), Associate Professor, Educational and Research Institute of Management, Psychology and Security, Lviv State University of Internal Affairs, Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1815-7554>

Kopytko M.

Doctor of science (Economics), Professor, Educational and Research Institute of Management, Psychology and Security, Lviv State University of Internal Affairs, Lviv, Ukraine
ORCID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0001-6598-3798>
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18195829>

Abstract

The article examines the role of human resources in ensuring the personnel security of enterprises in the context of European integration, digitalization of the economy, and the development of smart technologies. It is argued that human resources are a strategic resource of an enterprise, determining its ability to function sustainably, adapt to external and internal challenges, and minimize personnel risks. The essence of human resource potential as a combination of professional, personal, and motivational characteristics of personnel, as well as their potential for development, is revealed. The main factors influencing the human resource potential of Ukrainian enterprises in the current conditions, in particular, military actions, economic instability, labor migration, and labor market transformation, are analyzed. Particular attention is paid to the relationship between human resource potential and the introduction of smart technologies that change the nature of work, increase the requirements for digital competencies, and shape new approaches to human resource management. The directions for the development of human resources potential are determined, which depend on the strategic decisions of management, corporate culture, and the level of digital maturity of the enterprise. It has been proven that a comprehensive combination of human resource development, use of smart technologies contributes and compliance control to strengthening human resource security, increasing labor productivity, and improving the competitiveness of enterprises. It is concluded that the formation of long-term human resource management strategies is a necessary condition for the sustainable development of Ukrainian enterprises in the current socio-economic realities.

Keywords: *personnel, human resources, enterprise, personnel security, smart technologies, human resources, European integration, professional skills.*

Relevance of the research topic. Human resources are a fundamental component of the functioning and development of an enterprise, as it is the staff that acts as the key bearer of knowledge, competencies, innovative ideas, and management decisions. In the context of the transformation processes taking place in the Ukrainian economy, the importance of effective human resource management as a strategic resource capable of ensuring the stability, competitiveness, and security of enterprises is growing. This is particularly important in the context of European integration, which is accompanied by the harmonization of personnel management standards, higher requirements for the quality of labor resources, and increased competition in the labor market. Under such conditions, human resources are viewed not only as the sum of the existing professional characteristics of employees, but also as a reserve for development that determines the long-term capabilities of an enterprise.

The relevance of researching human resource potential is also determined by the active implementation of smart technologies, the digitization of business processes, and the transition to innovative management models. The development of automation, the use of big data, artificial intelligence, and digital platforms is changing the requirements for personnel and, at the

same time, creating new risks in the field of corporate human resource security. In this context, human resources play a key role in ensuring personnel security, as the level of competence, motivation, loyalty, and adaptability of personnel directly affects the ability of an enterprise to counter internal and external threats. Thus, research into the role of human resources in ensuring corporate security in the context of European integration and the development of smart technologies is timely and necessary for the formation of effective human resources policies and the sustainable development of modern organizations.

Analysis of recent studies and publications. The issues of formation, development, and effective use of human resources are widely represented in contemporary scientific research by domestic and foreign scholars. In particular, in the works of G. V. Dolgaya and O. A. Khytrova [1], the human resource potential of enterprises is considered as a key factor in improving the efficiency and competitiveness of activities, with an emphasis on methods for evaluating the effectiveness of its use. N. V. Gryshchenko and L. S. Zemlyana [2; 7] focus on the organizational and economic foundations of the formation and development of human resources in the agricultural sector, emphasizing the strategic nature of human resource management. The competency-

based approach to personnel management as the basis for the adaptation of enterprises to modern challenges is revealed in the studies of S. V. Leskova and O. I. Pavlikivska, L. O. Galinyak [3; 6], where human resources are considered in relation to innovative development and the long-term strategy of the enterprise. The theoretical aspects of the essence of human resources and their place in the system of public and corporate governance are substantiated in the works of N. V. Oliinyk [5]. Certain aspects of staff motivation, leadership, and the impact of modern technologies on human resource management have been studied in the works of T. Kornieieva, O. Syniuk, N. Shevchenko, N. Marushko, and Z. Zhyvko, N. Shevchenko, and H. Leskiv [4; 8], which emphasize the role of the human factor in conditions of crisis, digitalization, and growing economic security risks. At the same time, despite significant scientific achievements, the issue of the role of human resources in ensuring the personnel security of enterprises in the context of European integration and the development of smart technologies requires further in-depth research.

The purpose of the article is to provide a theoretical justification and comprehensive study of the role of human resources in ensuring the personnel security of enterprises in the context of European integration and the development of smart technologies, as well as to identify priority areas for its formation and development, taking into account current socio-economic challenges.

Presentation of the main material. Today, in the context of war, economic uncertainty, and labor migration, the issue of human resources for Ukrainian enterprises is extremely important and strategic, since it is human resources that determine the ability of organizations to maintain stability, adapt to crisis changes, and ensure the continuity of economic activity. Mass population displacement, a shortage of skilled personnel, an increase in the socio-psychological burden on employees, and intensified competition for human capital significantly complicate personnel management processes and increase personnel security risks. Under such conditions, the effective formation, preservation, and development of human resources potential becomes a key prerequisite for economic recovery, ensuring the innovative development of enterprises, and their integration into the European economic space.

In modern sources, the concept of “human resource potential” is interpreted on the basis of two characteristics. The first is related to the quantitative and qualitative characteristics of the enterprise's personnel, reflecting their professional knowledge, skills, experience, competence, level of education, and working capacity, which directly affect the results of the organization's activities. The second is based on the potential for staff development, in particular the ability of employees to learn, adapt, innovate, and effectively implement the enterprise's strategic goals in conditions of dynamic socio-economic change [1-3; 5].

Human resource potential is the totality of all the qualifications, professional, psychological, and physical capabilities of an enterprise's personnel (or region, country) to achieve its strategic goals, including knowledge, experience, skills, motivation, and ability to innovate, which are measured by both quantitative (age, seniority, staff turnover) and qualitative (competence, creativity) indicators that form the basis of competitiveness. This is a dynamic value that is constantly evolving through training and experience. Its key components are:

- quantitative - number, age and gender structure, length of service, staff turnover rate;
- qualitative - education, professional training, experience, skills, level of qualification, creativity, communication and psychological characteristics, motivation, ability for self-improvement, teamwork [4; 7].

Human resource potential in the context of European integration means expanding opportunities to develop highly qualified personnel capable of working in accordance with European standards of management, labor, and corporate responsibility. It involves adapting the human resource management system to the requirements of the European labor market, improving the professional, language, and digital skills of employees, and developing mobility and continuous learning. At the same time, human resources potential becomes a tool for integrating enterprises into the European economic space, ensuring increased competitiveness, personnel security, and innovative capacity in the context of intensifying international competition.

In addition, human resource potential under European integration creates opportunities for the transfer of best management practices, modern HR technologies, and advanced models of professional development. It also enhances enterprises' ability to attract, retain, and develop talent in a competitive international labor market. Ultimately, strengthening human resource potential supports sustainable growth, organizational resilience, and effective integration of enterprises into the European economic environment.

With regard to compliance control, the development of human resource potential ensures more effective implementation of control programs by increasing the level of legal awareness, professional responsibility, and ethical culture of employees. This contributes to reducing regulatory risks, ensuring compliance with European business standards, and forming a transparent system of corporate governance.

Thus, it can be argued that human resources are a group of highly qualified employees (human capital) who, with effective communication, the use of soft and hard skills, and innovative and creative activity, are capable of ensuring the effective functioning and development of an enterprise, institution, or organization. Human resource potential also has a significant impact on the human resource security of an enterprise (table 1).

Table 1.

The role of human resource potential in ensuring human resource security

Aspect of the role of human resource potential	Content in the context of ensuring personnel security
Strategic	Human resource potential forms the basis of long-term personnel security of an enterprise, ensuring its resilience, adaptability to external threats, and maintenance of competitive positions.
Human resource	The availability of qualified personnel reduces the risks of staff shortages, high employee turnover, and the loss of key specialists.
Competency-based	The level of professional knowledge, skills, and abilities of employees determines the enterprise's capacity to counter internal and external personnel-related threats effectively.
Motivational	A high level of human resource potential contributes to employee loyalty, reduces conflict, and minimizes opportunistic behavior within the organization.
Innovative	Human resource potential ensures staff readiness for the implementation of smart technologies, digitalization, and innovative management solutions.
Adaptive	The ability of personnel to respond quickly to crisis conditions, labor market changes, and European integration requirements enhances personnel security.
Socio-psychological	Developed human resource potential promotes workforce stability, reduces stress, and maintains productivity under conditions of uncertainty.
Security-oriented	Human resource potential acts as a tool for preventing internal threats, including information leakage, decreased discipline, and managerial risks.

Human resources are a strategic resource that determines an enterprise's ability to prevent personnel threats, ensure staff stability, and adapt to internal and external challenges. Effective formation and development of human resources contribute to strengthening personnel security and sustainable development of enterprises.

Regardless of the type of activity and the number of employees, the human resource potential of an enterprise has the following characteristics:

- comprehensive and systematic formation of personnel;
- combination of existing and potential capabilities of employees;
- dynamism and ability to develop and reproduce;
- dependence on the level of professional training, motivation, and experience of personnel;
- focus on achieving the strategic goals of the enterprise;
- interconnection with the external environment and internal conditions of the organization's functioning;

– decisive influence on the competitiveness and personnel security of the enterprise.

At the same time, an important component of the development and management of the enterprise's human resources potential is the identification of areas and stages of staff motivation and development, which requires a systematic approach to the formation of an effective human resources policy, taking into account the strategic goals of the organization. This approach includes assessing the current level of employee competencies, identifying their potential, developing professional training programs, and promoting professional development and career growth. Motivational mechanisms aimed at increasing staff interest in work results, building loyalty, and reducing personnel risks play an important role, which together contributes to the sustainable development of the enterprise and strengthens its personnel security.

Human resource development involves the following areas (Figure 1), which directly depend on management and business owners, development strategies, and corporate culture.

Fig. 1. The main areas of development of the company's human resources potential

The importance of developing human resources for Ukrainian enterprises is particularly acute in the context of war, economic instability, European integration processes, and active labor migration, as it is the personnel that determines the ability of organizations to maintain stability, competitiveness, and personnel security. The shortage of qualified personnel, growing demands for professional and digital competencies, and the need to quickly adapt to changes in the market environment necessitate the systematic development of employees' knowledge, skills, and motivation. Under these conditions, investing in human resource development becomes a strategic priority that ensures the innovative development of enterprises, the effective implementation of business strategies, and the integration of Ukrainian companies into the European economic space.

Given the current state of digitalization of economic and business processes, human resources are directly linked to the development and application of smart technologies, as it is the staff who are the key factor in their effective implementation and use. Smart technologies are changing the nature of work, increasing the requirements for digital competencies, analytical thinking, and the ability of employees to learn and

adapt quickly. In turn, the level of human resource development determines an enterprise's readiness for digital transformation, automation of management decisions, and ensuring personnel security, which is especially important in conditions of instability and growing technological risks.

The interconnection and strategic importance of using smart technologies in conjunction with human resources potential involves:

- improving the efficiency of personnel management through the automation of HR processes and data-driven management decisions;
- the development of digital and professional competencies of employees necessary for working in a digital economy;
- the reduction of human resource risks and the strengthening of human resource security through transparency, control, and forecasting of human resource processes;
- the improvement of labor productivity and task performance quality through the implementation of smart solutions;

- ensuring the adaptability of personnel to changes in the business environment and technological transformations;
- forming an innovative corporate culture focused on continuous learning and development;
- supporting the strategic development of the enterprise and its competitiveness in the context of European integration and the digitalization of the economy.

It should be noted that today, the human resources potential of Ukrainian enterprises is influenced by a significant number of factors that hinder both its development and its ability to ensure personnel security, develop smart technologies, and implement new human resources development strategies. These factors include military action, economic instability, demographic losses, and mass labor migration of qualified specialists. Additional constraints include limited financial resources of enterprises, reduced investment activity, and insufficient digital and managerial competencies of personnel. Taken together, this complicates the formation of long-term human resources potential, increases human resources risks, and requires a review of approaches to human resources management in light of current challenges.

It is advisable to identify areas for improving the human resource potential of enterprises in the context of European integration, which are systematic and long-term in nature. These areas include harmonizing approaches to human resource management with European standards, developing competency models focused on innovation and digital maturity, and fostering a culture of continuous professional learning. An important theoretical aspect is rethinking the role of personnel policy as a tool not only for personnel development, but also for ensuring the personnel security of enterprises in the context of an open European labor market. The implementation of these areas contributes to increasing the adaptability of human resources, strengthening the competitive positions of enterprises, and their integration into the European economic space.

Conclusion. The study substantiates the strategic role of human resources as a key factor in ensuring the personnel security of enterprises in the context of European integration, digitalization, and socio-economic instability. It has been established that effective management and development of human resources contribute to increasing the adaptability of enterprises, reducing human resource risks, and creating conditions for the implementation of smart technologies. It has been

proven that combining human resources with modern digital personnel management tools enhances the competitiveness and sustainability of enterprises in crisis conditions. The formation of long-term personnel development strategies, taking into account military challenges, labor migration, and the shortage of qualified personnel, is of particular relevance. Prospects for further research include the development of practical mechanisms for assessing the level of personnel security, the impact of smart technologies on the development of human resources, and the formation of adaptive personnel management models for Ukrainian enterprises.

References:

1. Dolgaya G. V., Khytrova O. A. (2022) Human resources of trade enterprises: essence and methods of assessing the effectiveness of its use. *Bulletin of Odessa National University. Series: Economics*, Vol. 27. Issue 1. Pp. 38-46.
2. Gryshchenko N. V. Organizational and economic foundations for developing strategies for building the human resource potential of businesses in the agricultural sector. *Economic Space*. 2022. No. 180. pp. 105–1107.
3. Leskova S. V. Competence-based approach to human resource management in modern enterprises. *Transformational Economics*. 2023. No. 3. Pp. 26–31.
4. Kornieieva, T., Syniuk, O., Shevchenko, N., Marushko, N. (2025) Dialectics of Job Stress and Organizational Peace. A critical study on the Management of Personnel Motivation in Enterprise Marketing in the Face of the Ukrainian War Experience. *Clio. Revista de Historia, Ciencias Humanas y Pensamiento Critico*, № 5(9), Pp. 711–739
5. Oliinyk, N. V. The essence of human resource potential: a theoretical aspect. *Public Administration: Improvement and Development*. 2023. No. 5. [URL:http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Duur_2023_5_20](http://nbuv.gov.ua/UJRN/Duur_2023_5_20)
6. Pavlikivska O. I., Galinyak L. O. Strategic provision of human resources for enterprises. *Galician Economic Herald*. 2022. No. 1. Pp. 103–111.
7. Zemlyana, L. S. (2022) Scientific and methodological basis of the human resource potential of an agricultural enterprise. *Innovation and Sustainability*. Issue 4. Pp. 207–214.
8. Zhyvko Z., Shevchenko N., Leskiv H. Features of determining the role of a leader in the project management system through modern technologies for evaluating his activities. *Digital Economy and Economic Security*. No. 5(20). 2025. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.32782/dees.20-38>